

A Software-Defined Connectivity Service for Multi-Cluster Cloud Native Applications

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Abstract

Containerization technologies have risen in popularity for deploying microservices applications in cloud-native environments, offering the benefits of traditional virtualization with reduced overhead. However, existing container networking solutions lack support for applications requiring isolated link-layer communications among containers in different clusters. These communications are fundamental to enable the seamless integration of cloud-native solutions in 5G and beyond networks. Accordingly, we present an SDN-enabled networking solution that supports the creation of isolated link-layer virtual networks between containers across different Kubernetes clusters by building virtual circuits that dynamically adapt to changes in the topology. In this article, we introduce our solution, highlighting its advantages over existing alternatives, and provide a comprehensive design overview. Additionally, we validate it through an experiment, offering a deeper understanding of its functionality. Our work fills an existing gap for applications with inter-cluster link-layer networking access requirements in the cloud-native ecosystem.

Keywords: Kubernetes, software-defined networking, multi-cluster

1. Introduction

Over the last few years, there has been a remarkably increasing trend in deploying software applications using the microservices architectural style (Thönes (2015); Balalaie et al. (2016)). Microservices architectures aim to deploy complex software services as groups of smaller autonomous services working together. These architectures have many benefits over traditional monolithic architectures such as higher resiliency, reduced time-to-market,

scalability, and easier adaptability to technological changes (Garrison and Nova (2017)). As a consequence, they have become significantly popular for applications running over cloud-native infrastructures.

The need to efficiently deploy software structured through microservices has led to the appearance of containerization technologies, that allow a host with a single operating system to run processes in spaces with isolated resources called containers. Containers provide many of the benefits traditional virtualization technologies have, without an unnecessary resource utilization overhead (Joy (2015)). The most notable effort to standardize these technologies is the Open Container Initiative specifications (The Linux Foundation (2015)). These specifications abstract the management of containers from their implementation, enabling the portability of containerized applications. This way, containers can be run and managed by different container runtimes, such as *containerd* or *CRI-O*, in different platforms. On top of that, there are tools that act as container orchestrators allowing the deployment of containers among one or more hosts and distributing the resources between them while facilitating their interconnection. One of the most popular container orchestrators is Kubernetes (also known as K8s), where the smallest deployable units are the Pods, which are groups of containers with, among other things, shared network resources. That means that, no matter how many containers run in a Pod, they will all share the same network interfaces and resources. In Kubernetes, the groups of nodes where Pods can be deployed are called *clusters* (Luksa (2017)).

In the majority of the applications, containers need to communicate with each other. There exist many solutions that provide networking capabilities for containers in Kubernetes clusters, but most of them are designed to support high-level application-layer protocols and mechanisms like HTTP or Remote Procedure Call APIs and, thus, enable connectivity at the network-layer (layer 3) or above. Although these solutions might be enough for many applications, others require containers to communicate at lower layers, i.e., at the link layer (layer 2). We proceed, now, to briefly describe some scenarios where this happens.

In Network Functions Virtualization (NFV) ecosystems (Yi et al. (2018)), the usage of containers can reduce the required computational resources and deployment times when compared to the usage of traditional virtual machines. In this case, some of the network functions, like routers, might need to operate at the layer 3, and, thus, require layer 2 connectivity between them. There are, additionally, other scenarios that require the deployment

of layer 2 network functions as containers running in different clusters. Some examples of such scenarios could be the deployment of a 5G core distributed among different clusters, or a distributed IP telephony or television service, where multicast technologies might be used. Moreover, scenarios where traffic engineering and non-IP technologies are used, like MPLS (Viswanathan et al. (2001)), also require layer 2 connectivity. Finally, layer 2 connectivity is needed when it is necessary to deploy a service where, for security reasons, the network must be segmented into several layer 2 networks and firewalls and other layer 2 security network functions must be deployed. In general, it allows users to utilize any already existing or future network stacks at the layer 3 or above. Some of the benefits of layer 2 solutions can also be obtained through the usage of network policies in layer 3 solutions, but that approach is not as flexible and powerful.

There are some freely available solutions that can be used to communicate Pods that run inside the same Kubernetes cluster, i.e., intra-cluster communications, at the link-layer. Some examples of these solutions are L2S-M (Gonzalez et al. (2023)), EdgeVPN.io (Subratie et al. (2023)) and Megalos(Scazzariello et al. (2020)). There is, however, a need for a solution that does the same for Pods running in different clusters, i.e., inter-cluster communications.

In this article, we present a new inter-cluster virtual link-layer networking solution for Kubernetes, that, through an orchestrator, allows service providers to have efficient multi-point link-layer connectivity between Pods in different Kubernetes clusters. The solution uses a scalable data-plane switching method based on the creation of virtual circuits. It does not replace, but rather complements, the local orchestrators in each cluster, and, thus, could potentially also be used to connect clusters running over different technological stacks, such as OpenStack (The OpenStack Community (2024)). This solution has not only been designed, but also implemented and experimentally validated.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides contextual information to the reader, describing the main concepts and technologies that are related to our work. Section 3 describes the design and implementation of the proposed solution. The results in section 4 provide the validation of our work. Finally, section 5 presents the main conclusions of this article and future lines of research.

2. Related work

2.1. Network virtualization

Network virtualization is a technology that allows creating virtual networks, i.e, networks composed of different virtual resources, over shared physical networks. With it, one physical network can be used by many other networks that are logically separated from each other. Virtual networks have benefits in different scenarios. In the case of network service providers and businesses, for example, they provide flexibility, agility, scalability and costs savings when compared to traditional physical networks deployments (Stallings (2015)).

It is one of the main enabler technologies for container networking. Containers run, in most of the use-cases, distributed across a potentially heterogeneous physical computing and networking infrastructure. Virtual networks allow their interconnection in a way that makes it logically independent of the underlying physical ones (Suo et al. (2018))

The virtualization can happen at different layers of the OSI model. A very powerful and common technique is the usage of tunneling protocols. Tunnels allow, for example, to encapsulate Ethernet frames (layer 2) into IP packet (layer 3). The virtualization of network through tunnels is extensively used in existing virtual networking solutions due to all the benefits it has (Han et al. (2015)). Some examples of tunneling protocols are VXLAN (Mahalingam et al. (2014)), used by the layer 3 Kubernetes solution *flannel* (Flannel Maintainer Community (2023)), GENEVE (Gross et al. (2020)), or GRE (Li et al. (2000)).

2.2. Traditional layer 2 VPN services

Virtual Private Network services allow creating virtual networks over public infrastructure. Some of them can be used over any arbitrary network, while others require the network connecting the different network endpoints to be fully controlled by the service providers. This is the case, for example, of the Virtual Private LAN Service (Rekhter and Kompella (2007), Lasserre and Kompella (2007)), which requires the use of MPLS in the core switching function, and, thus, cannot be used when the clusters are connected through an uncontrolled network like the Internet.

There are many different VPN technologies that cover many different needs, some of them providing interconnection at the link-layer and others

at higher layers. Traditional VPN services, however, only provide the transport functionality of virtual networking. This means, some of them could be used to create virtual link-layer networks between containers. One could, for example, use OpenVPN (OpenVPN Project (2024)) to connect two containers through a virtual link-layer network. This approach, however, would require configuring everything inside each endpoint. The solution we propose includes an orchestrator that manages the network configuration according to the virtual networks defined by the service providers and integrates into multi-cluster Kubernetes ecosystems.

2.3. Multi-cluster virtual layer 3 networking solutions

There are many freely available solutions that allow communicating Pods that run in different Kubernetes clusters. Most of them, however, are only focused on layer 3 connectivity. With these solutions, Pods can transmit and receive IP packets to and from other Pods. This, as explained in section 1 is not suitable for many scenarios where Pods require layer 2 connectivity. Some examples of these solutions are Submariner (The Submariner Contributors (2024)); Antrea¹ (The Antrea Contributors (2024)); Cilium (The Cilium Authors and Isovalent (2024)); or Weave Net (Weaveworks (2021)).

Some of these solutions give the user some control of how the traffic flows through the created networks and provide network isolation, but it is not as complete as what one can get from installing their own layer 3 network functions over a layer 2 networking solution. Some benefits of layer 2 virtual networking over layer 3 virtual networking with policies in multi-tenancy scenarios, like the scalability are discussed in Potter and De Groot (2019).

Other solutions provide virtual networking service at layers above the layer 3, like Skupper (The Skupper Authors (2024)), that works at the application layer, or Istio (The Istio Authors (2024)), that allows routing at the transport and application layers.

2.4. Multi-cluster virtual layer 2 networking solutions

There are also some layer 2 virtual networking solutions that are worth mentioning.

Open Virtual Network (OVN) is an open-source virtual networking solution that provides network connectivity and services for virtualized envi-

¹Since v1.9.0

ronments, i.e., container and virtual machine environments (The OVN contributors (2024)). It is built on top of the Open vSwitch (OVS) software. It can work both with layer 3 or layer 2 networks and can be integrated with Kubernetes as a networking plugin through the OVN-Kubernetes feature for intra-cluster connectivity.

To encapsulate the frames, OVN uses the GENEVE tunneling protocol rather than other options like VXLAN or GRE. The packets are switched based on both a GENEVE tunnel identifier and the MAC addresses, which requires the intermediate nodes to know the MAC addresses of the containers connected to the edge nodes. In the solution we propose, in multi-point networks, the intermediate nodes in the path between clusters do not need to know the MAC addresses of the containers. Additionally, OVN requires the use of Open vSwitches, while our solution is compatible with any switch supporting OpenFlow². OpenFlow is an SDN southbound protocol standardized by the Open Networking Foundation (Open Networking Foundation (2015)). It allow the SDN controllers to, among other things, connect to the programmable switches in a network to get information about them and install forwarding rules in them to control how the data-plane traffic flows. It, thus, allows to control the packets flow through the networks from a centralized component. It defines a pipeline that in turn defines how each packet is affected by each forwarding rule. The specific details of how OpenFlow works are not relevant to understand the work we present here.

In Rafiq et al. (2020), the authors describe an architecture to connect Pods inside the same Kubernetes cluster through layer 2 virtual networks, although their conclusions can also be applied to the multi-cluster scenarios. They use network intents and the tunnel ID to multiplex networks, in an approach that is similar to the one presented in this article in some aspects. Nonetheless, as with traditional VLAN scenarios, packet switching is done by looking at both the VLAN ID and the destination MAC address even in the intermediate nodes.

In Gonzalez et al. (2023), an architecture to support intra-cluster and inter-cluster communications is proposed. The intra-cluster part is designed and implemented, but the inter-cluster part is only mentioned as an idea. This idea is evolved, designed and implemented in this article.

²OpenFlow version 1.3 in the current implementation

3. Proposed solution

3.1. Architecture

The proposed solution allows the connection of Pods running in different Kubernetes clusters, providing them link-layer visibility between each other through the creation (and deletion when needed) of virtual link-layer networks. It is enabled by SDN technologies and comprises two main elements: the Network Edge Device (NED) overlay network and the inter-cluster Connectivity Orchestrator (IDCO).

NEDs are programmable switching functions in charge of forwarding the traffic between clusters. Each cluster containing Pods that require communicating with other Pods in different clusters must have at least one NED. NEDs are interconnected through security-protected IP tunnels, thereby creating a NED overlay network that interconnects all the clusters. Besides, each NED has several ports that are used to connect it to the intra-cluster networks in its cluster.

The IDCO functions as an SDN controller with a northbound interface (IDCO-NBI) and a southbound interface (IDCO-SBI). All the NEDs connect to the IDCO via the IDCO-SBI, which is currently implemented with OpenFlow. The IDCO is accessed by service providers, i.e., the entities that want to create inter-cluster virtual networks, through the IDCO-NBI using a custom HTTP REST API inspired in the ETSI GS NFV-IFA 032 MSCS Management Interface (Network Functions Virtualisation ETSI Industry Specification Group (2019)).

Figure 1 illustrates the architecture of our service, considering an exemplifying scenario where multiple clusters exist, each of them with one or more NEDs. In this scenario, two inter-cluster virtual networks have been created by the service providers. The Pods in each cluster are connected to their corresponding NEDs through their available access ports. Our service is in charge of providing connectivity between NED ports allocated to the Pods, whereas the task of connecting the Pods to those ports belongs to the intra-cluster networking solution used in each cluster. One option to provide such connectivity is to use a Kubernetes CNI plugin supporting Linux Bridges (such as Multus), as shown in section 4. This option is suitable for simple scenarios where there is only a single node in each cluster with a single NED instance. More complex scenarios with multiple NED instances per cluster can be supported by full intra-cluster networking solutions.

Figure 1: Exemplifying scenario for the proposed architecture with two virtual networks: a multi-point network in green and a point-to-point network in purple. The virtual circuit for the point-to-point network is shown. In the multi-point network, only the tree-shaped virtual circuit of POD 1 is shown. The technologies used in the implementation of each component are shown.

When a service provider wants to connect two or more Pods located in different clusters, it uses the IDCO-NBI to request the creation of an inter-cluster virtual network. The request includes information for identifying the clusters where the Pods are deployed, along with additional information regarding the virtual network, i.e., a human-friendly name and a description. Figure 2 shows an example of a descriptor. Subsequently, the IDCO checks the available ports in each of the NEDs of those clusters, randomly chooses one for each of them and sends their identifiers back to the service provider in a response along with a virtual network identifier that can be used by the service provider to identify the network against the IDCO for future requests. The service provider may then use the information received to connect the Pods in each cluster to the NED ports chosen by the IDCO, using the networking solution running in each cluster (e.g., through the Multus CNI or L2S-M). Simultaneously, the IDCO creates a set of virtual circuits on the NED overlay by installing some flow rules that enable the data-plane inter-

cluster communications between those NED ports. Section 3.2 describes how those virtual circuits are created.

```
1 mscsName: iptv-europe
2 mscsDescription: Network for an IPTV service distributed across
   ↪ the clusters in Madrid, Munich and London
3 mscsEndpoints:
4   - domainName: madrid
5     localNet: net-iptv-madrid
6   - domainName: munich
7     localNet: net-iptv-munich
8   - domainName: london
9     localNet: net-iptv-london
10
```

Figure 2: An example of a descriptor for a 3-point network connecting the clusters with names "madrid", "munich" and "london". The local-net field in each of the points indicates to the IDCO which local networks in each cluster it must connect to the inter-cluster network.

Finally, a service provider may request the deletion of an existing virtual network through the IDCO-NBI, providing the virtual network identifier returned by the IDCO at creation time. Upon receiving this request, the IDCO deletes the flow rules that were installed in the NEDs for that virtual network and releases the allocated resources.

3.2. An efficient and adaptive data-plane

One of the main tasks of the IDCO is to build virtual circuits on top of the NED overlay by installing the needed rules in the NEDs. In this section, we describe how those virtual circuits are created to enable inter-cluster link-layer communications in an efficient and adaptive manner.

The NED overlay comprises all the NEDs of the system connected through IP tunnels. As previously commented, NEDs implement link-layer switching functionalities, exchanging layer-2 frames over the point-to-point links provided by the IP tunnels. These IP tunnels use the VXLAN protocol in our service, although other protocols could be used.

Each tunnel is characterized by the endpoints IP addresses and UDP ports. The Virtual Network Identifier of each tunnel (VNI), called the tunnel id in the OpenFlow 1.3 specification, is not set to a fixed number, but is

rather left as a field the flow rules that control how frames go in and out of the IP tunnels, must get and set. This allows the creation of tunnel-id-based virtual circuits on the NED overlay, i.e., virtual circuits that are characterized by the tunnel id of the packets that traverse the NED overlay tunnels. To understand how these virtual circuits provide inter-cluster communications, it is necessary to differentiate between two main cases: Point-to-Point networks, where only two clusters are connected and Multi-Point networks, where more than two clusters are connected. Notice that this differentiation is based on the number of clusters that are connected through the network and not on the number of Pods in the network, which means a network that connects two clusters is considered to be a point-to-point network for the IDCO, independently of the number of Pods that will be connected to the network in those clusters.

In point-to-point networks, the IDCO chooses a random tunnel id and creates a virtual circuit that connects both NEDs and is characterized by that tunnel id. This way, every frame that enters one of the NED ports, travels through the network encapsulated in VXLAN packets that have that tunnel id and until it is outputted to the other port. The built virtual circuit can go through multiple intermediate NEDs following the least-cost path between NEDs, using the hop count as the cost metric.

In multi-point networks that connect N clusters, the IDCO chooses N random tunnel ids. Subsequently, it creates a tree-shaped circuit for each of the ports that connects it to all the other ports in the network. Therefore, it creates N tree-shaped virtual circuits, each of them characterized by a tunnel id. For each of the ports, its tree is used for two purposes:

- To deliver the unicast frames destined to that port from any of the other ports.
- To deliver the broadcast and multicast frames that come from that port to all the other ports.

Unlike in point-to-point networks, in multi-point networks, the IDCO needs to know where each Pod is located to be able to install the needed flow rules in the NEDs to forward the frames to the correct destination port by using its tree-shaped virtual circuit. To do so, it learns the MAC addresses and location of the Pods of the network by acting as an ARP proxy, i.e., when a Pod sends an ARP request or reply, it is sent by the NED in its cluster to the IDCO through the IDCO-SBI, that learns the Pod's address

and location, installs the flow rules that put the frames directed to it into its tree-shaped circuit in all the NEDs and finally delivers the ARP to the network again through the IDCO-SBI interface. This process is explained in more detail in section 4 using the validation test as an example.

In Figure 1, a point-to-point network and a multi-point network have been created. The virtual circuit for the point-to-point network is shown. The multi-point network has three tree-shaped virtual circuits, one for each of the clusters. For simplicity, only one of them is shown. This circuit is used by the other Pods in the multi-point network to send unicast frames to POD 1 and from POD 1 to send broadcast packets to the other Pods in its network. Each virtual circuit uses a different tunnel id, thus allowing them all to coexist in the NED overlay network. In the point-to-point network, there is only one linear virtual circuit and thus, only one tunnel id is used. In the multi-point network, there are three tree-shaped virtual circuits (only one of them is shown), which implies three tunnel ids are used.

This tunnel-id-based switching approach has several benefits over a mac-based switching approach. Firstly, in point-to-point networks, the IDCO does not need to learn the MAC addresses of the Pods in the network. The virtual circuit is setup once and remains constant independently of the number of Pods in each cluster. Secondly, in multi-point networks, the intermediate NEDs, i.e., the NEDs that forward traffic for the network but do not have any ports that belong to that network, do not need to know the MAC addresses of the Pods that act as communication endpoints. Only the NEDs at the edge of the network have flow rules that contain MAC addresses. This makes the network more scalable and efficient because the number of flows in the intermediate NEDs does not increase with the number of Pods attached to the virtual networks. Finally, it allows pre-creating the virtual circuits before the Pods are discovered. In multi-point networks, when the IDCO discovers a new Pod, it only needs to install some rules in the NEDs that have ports that belong to the virtual network.

On top of that, this service is designed in a way that allows the data-plane to adapt to changes. To do so, the IDCO periodically communicates with the NEDs to instruct them to flood the overlay network with Link Layer Discovery Protocol (LLDP) packets with a special reserved tunnel id. This protocol allows network devices to obtain some information about the neighbors in their networks. When the NEDs receive the LLDP packets coming from other NED, they send them back to the IDCO. This way, the IDCO is able to detect any changes in the topology.

When a change in the topology is noticed by the IDCO, it finds the new shortest path and reinstall the needed rules. If the change does not affect a specific rule, that rule will not be changed. This way, if there is a link failure or a new link appears in the NED overlay, our service will be able change the virtual networks in real time so that they follow the new shortest path, if one is available. Additionally, this approach enables the future development of more complex services that might want to choose new paths for the network as a consequence of other factors, like the congestion of each link.

It is interesting to remark that, although this solution is designed for inter-cluster communications, the idea of using tunnel-id-based virtual circuits could also be used for communications within a cluster of multiple separated compute nodes or other applications.

A reader could question the necessity of such a data-plane solution, when a link-layer multi-cluster network could be built by connecting several simple switches together through IP tunnels. There are, however, several benefits in our solution:

- It allows having several virtual link-layer networks between clusters that work independently and are completely isolated from each other. Accordingly, the efficiency and security of the overall system is increased.
- As the data plane is built using virtual circuits, all the loops are inherently avoided³. Therefore, it is possible to have a redundant switched network without the need of additional protocols like the Spanning Tree Protocol. Additionally, unlike in the Spanning Tree Protocol, the built trees are source-based.
- Broadcast frames are efficiently delivered to the destination nodes, meaning they are only cloned in the nodes where it is strictly necessary, taking into account the points that belong to each virtual network.
- It uses an SDN-enabled centralized control plane, which eases the deployment of new networking and security technologies.

³As long as there are not loops in the intra-cluster networks.

3.3. The implementation

The solution has been fully implemented according to the proposed design. The implementation is completely functional. Figure 1 shows the technologies used in each of the components.

The NEDs are implemented using Open vSwitch (The Open vSwitch Contributors (2024)). In our implementation, they run as Kubernetes Pods that are connected to the Pods in their respective clusters through the intra-cluster networks. The intra-cluster networks are realized using Linux Bridges. To do so additional network interfaces can be added to the NEDs and the Pods network namespaces through Multus (Kubernetes Network Plumbing Working Group (2023)) and the "bridge" CNI plugin. In a scenario where each cluster has more than one node and the Pods that require inter-cluster connectivity must be deployed in a different node to the NED, it would be necessary to use a more advanced solution, like L2S-M (Gonzalez et al. (2023)). In order to run the OVSs as Pods, a custom image is used.

The topology of the NED overlay is assumed to be already established; it could be established either manually, or automatically by an additional component.

The IDCO is implemented as a custom internal application that runs within an instance of the Open Network Operating System (ONOS) version 2.7.0 (Open Networking Foundation (2021)). It additionally uses other official ONOS application: the OpenFlow drivers, that allow abstracting the implementation from the SDN southbound protocol; and the Link Discovery Provider, that uses the LLDP protocol to discover the topology of the network. As the IDCO runs inside ONOS, it can be deployed in any running instance of it, e.g., in a Pod or directly running on a host or virtual machine. It has an internal in-memory database where all the information of the virtual networks is stored. It reacts to all the changes in the network through event listeners that execute the needed actions through a synchronized multi-threaded executor service.

The custom application implements the custom HTTP REST API for the IDCO-NBI, creates and deletes the virtual networks and acts as the ARP proxy that learns the MAC addresses in multi-point networks. Additionally, it creates two new intents in ONOS, one for the point-to-point networks and another one for the Multi-Point networks, with their correspondent compilers. The reason behind creating these two new intents is that the network intents included by default in ONOS are not designed for our purposes and using them makes the implementation much more difficult and less scalable. The

point-to-point and single-point-to-multi-point intents that come by default with ONOS do not consider the tunneling between NEDs and thus do not make use of the tunnel id associated as a way to differentiate packets.

The newly created intents are integrated in the ONOS Intent Framework via the Intent Extension Service. The application is, thus, partially aligned with the Intent-Based Networking (IBN) paradigm, although it is very far from the final objectives of real IBN applications, that might require of more advanced technologies like Machine Learning (Clemm et al. (2022)). When a service provider sends a network descriptor to the IDCO, it gets transformed to an intent whose inputs are the NED ports that need to be connected. That intent is then translated into installable network rules after calculating the needed paths. The main advantage of using these intents is that ONOS keeps track of the network elements affected by each intent and manages the lifecycle of the intents in relation to it. This way, if a link fails, ONOS automatically re-compiles the intents that were using that link so that they can find a new optimal path. This way, ONOS provides a basic mechanism of intent monitoring and verification, although one that is far for what is expected in advanced IBN applications. Inside the new intents, the ONOS Flow Objectives API is used. This API allows developing SDN applications that are pipeline-independent, meaning they do not depend on the specific SDN southbound protocol in use.

When the IDCO receives a request to create a point-to-point network through the HTTP REST API of the IDCO-NBI , it chooses one available port in each of the network domains indicated in the request (unless the user has already chosen one) and submits an intent for that point-to-point network. The intent is then compiled using the code we have developed. This code calculates the least cost path between the chosen ports and creates the needed rules for the edge and intermediate NEDs. Similarly, when it receives a descriptor for a multi-point network and after choosing the ports, it submits a multi-point network intent. In the compilation process of this intent, all the source-based trees from all the points to all the other points are calculated and then the needed rules for each of them are installed. At this point the broadcast packets can already flow through the network in an efficient way, meaning they are only duplicated in the points they really need to be replicated at and they are only sent to the clusters that belong to the network of the source Pod. In the case the unicast packets, when the IDCO learns the location of a host through the ARP packets, it installs several rules in the NEDs that allow packets addressed to that host to get inserted into the

Figure 3: The validation experiment scenario virtual machines and their networks. Each VM forms a Kubernetes cluster where the needed Pods are deployed (the NEDs are also deployed as Pods).

corresponding virtual circuit to reach it.

4. Experimental Validation

We have carried out an experiment to validate the developed solution, as well as to dive deeper into the concepts explained in the previous section in a practical way. The execution has taken place in the 5TONIC laboratory, an advanced research center founded by Telefónica and IMDEA Networks.

4.1. Experiment setup

The scenario used to perform this validation is shown in Figure 3. In this scenario, there are four Kubernetes clusters: K8s 1 to K8s 4 and six Pods: A, B, C, D, E, and F, deployed on the different clusters. A service provider wants to connect Pod A, Pod B, and Pod C through a link-layer virtual network we will refer to as "the blue network"; and Pod D, Pod E, and Pod F through another one we will denominate "the red network". To configure the scenario, all the NEDs have in their network namespace an interface that is connected to a L3 network that forms the data plane underlay. The NED overlay network formed by VXLAN tunnels is deployed over this underlay network. At the same time, each VM has an interface that is connected to a L3 network used for the control plane. The NEDs can use this interface to connect to the IDC0 through the flannel CNI plugin (Flannel Maintainer Community (2023)) that NATs the connections. The

IDCO shares the network namespace with the VM it is deployed at and therefore can directly access this interface. The chosen NED overlay network is shown in Figure 4. Our solution only requires one NED per cluster and does not cover the intra-cluster communications. For that reason, we have decided to use single-noded clusters in the validation and this way focus only on the inter-cluster networking functionality, that is not affected by it.

Figure 4: The chosen NED overlay for the experiment

The steps we have followed to set up the scenario are:

1. Five virtual machines have been deployed in an OpenStack cloud platform. Four of them (VMs with K8s 1, 2, 3, and 4 in Figure 3) have been provided with two network interfaces that are configured to have L3 connectivity with their corresponding interfaces in the other machines (this connectivity is supported through separate OpenStack networks). In each of these VMs, one of the interfaces is kept in the VM main network namespace, and will later be used by the NED to communicate with the IDCO (control plane IDCO-SBI) through the Flannel CNI plugin. The other interface will be moved into the NED network namespace through the "host-device" plugin and Multus and will be used for the data plane. The fifth VM (VM with K8s 5) has a single interface that is kept in the VM main network namespace. This interface will be used for IDCO control-plane communications. In this case,

given the Pods are deployed in the same nodes as the NEDs, we are using the "bridge" CNI plugin to connect them. In scenarios with more nodes where the Pods and NED must be in different nodes, a link-layer networking solution would be needed. In general, our solution is CNI-agnostic and independent of the intra-cluster communications, which means it is not necessary to use Flannel or any of the other CNI plugins we are using. It could also be possible, by using the Kubernetes services, to have only one interface in each virtual machine for both the control and data planes instead of two.

2. Kubeadm has been installed and configured in the five virtual machines to have a running Kubernetes cluster. The fact that real virtual machines with Kubernetes are being used for the validation adds realism to it.
3. In the first four clusters, the corresponding Pods have been deployed, including a NED instance. The Pods have been assigned an IP address for the network they belong to (blue or red).
4. The VXLANs inside the NEDs have been manually configured to form the NED overlay network.
5. In the fifth cluster, the IDCO has been deployed. To do so, a Pod with the official ONOS 2.7 image has been used where the compiled custom IDCO app has been installed and configured.
6. To deploy the red and blue networks, two YAML descriptors have been created and sent to the IDCO through the IDCO NBI. *curl* has been used as the HTTP client to send the descriptors.

After receiving the network descriptors, the IDCO proceeds to calculate the tree-shaped circuit paths and install the rules in the NEDs that are part of those paths. These virtual circuits allow building the red and blue networks on top of the same NED overlay network while being isolated from each other.

The switching rules in each of the switches for the red network after the IDCO has established the virtual circuits are shown in Table 1.

4.2. Experiment execution

After some time, the Pods B, C and D start transmitting data traffic with the patterns described in Table 2.

In the blue network, all the traffic is addressed to a broadcast MAC address. This means the packets start flowing through the virtual circuits

Matching criteria				Actions		
Protocol	Input	Dst. MAC	Tunnel ID	Set Tunnel ID	Output	Table
ARP	PORT_D	Any	None	None	To IDCO	0
Any	PORT_D	Broadcast	None	5	NED_3	0
Any	NED_3	Any	5	None	PORT_E	0
Any	NED_3	Any	4	None	PORT_E	0
Any	NED_3	Any	3	None	PORT_E	0
Any	PORT_E	Any	4	4	NED_3	1
Any	PORT_E	Any	3	3	NED_3	1

(a) NED 4

Matching criteria				Actions		
Protocol	Input	Dst. MAC	Tunnel ID	Set Tunnel ID	Output	Table
Any	NED_4	Any	5	5	NED_1 NED_2	0
Any	NED_2 NED_1	Any	5	5	NED_4	0
Any	NED_2	Any	4	4	NED_4	0
Any	NED_4	Any	4	4	NED_2	0
Any	NED_1	Any	3	3	NED_4	0
Any	NED_4	Any	3	3	NED_1	0

(b) NED 3

Table 1: Rules for the red network in NEDs 3 and 4 before the Pods have started to communicate with each other. The VNI 3 corresponds to the VNI 3 in Figure 6

that were established by the IDCO when the network was created, without the need of any other action.

Source IP address	Destination IP address	Protocol	Goodput [Mb/s]
B	Broadcast	UDP	1
C	Broadcast	UDP	2
D	E	UDP	3

Table 2: Experiment network traffic

In the red network, the traffic is unicast. In this case, the process is different. The virtual circuits to reach each cluster were established by the IDCO when the network was created too, but it is still necessary to install the rules that put the packets into those circuits based on their destination MAC addresses. The sequence of events is the following one:

1. D sends an ARP request to discover the MAC address of E.

2. The NED 4 receives the ARP request and sends it to the IDCO encapsulated in an OpenFlow PacketIn message that carries, not only the packet but also other information, like the port it originally came from.
3. The IDCO receives the ARP request packet and executes two actions in parallel:
 - It sends the packet to all the other ports in the red network, i.e., the ports where E and F are connected
 - As it knows which is the port the packet originally came from, it learns that is the port D is accessible at. With that information, it installs in all the other NEDs that have ports that belong to the red network, i.e., the NEDs 1, 2 and 4, a rule that makes them forward all the traffic addressed to the MAC address of D through the tree-shaped virtual circuit of the port D is connected to.
4. E receives the ARP request and sends an ARP reply. The reply is also forwarded to the IDCO, that learns the location of E and, as with D, installs the rules in the NEDs of the network for Pod E. Additionally, it forwards the ARP reply to the port D is located at.

In our experiment, this process is done in less than a second and, upon completion, D starts sending the unicast UDP packets to E. The flow tables at the NEDs comprising the network edge of the red network (NEDs 1, 2 and 4) will contain entries for Pods E and D MAC address. The NED 3 will have the same number of entries as before because it is an intermediate node for that network. The paths followed by the packets are shown in Figure 5 (a). The switching rules in NEDs 3 and 4 for the red network after this process is done are shown in Table 3. As can be observed, the amount of rules in NED 3, which is an intermediate NED, does not change when a new MAC address is learned. In fact, the rules in NED 3 will remain the same no matter how many Pods are using the networks.

After 15 seconds, the link between the NED 1 and the NED 3 is blocked, which makes the LLDP packets sent by the NED 1 to not arrive to the NED 3 and vice versa. As a consequence, the IDCO notices the link is down, which triggers a re-computation of the shortest paths for the tree-shaped virtual circuits followed by re-installation of the rules in the NEDs as needed, making the traffic flow through them. The new paths followed by the packets are shown in Figure 5 (b).

Another 15 seconds into the experiment (in second 30), the blocked link is unblocked. Consequently, the IDCO starts re-computing the new shortest

Matching criteria				Actions		
Protocol	Input	Dst. MAC	Tunnel ID	Set Tunnel ID	Output	Table
ARP	PORT_D	Any	None	None	To IDCO	0
Any	PORT_D	Broadcast	None	5	NED_3	0
Any	NED_3	Any	5	None	PORT_E	0
Any	NED_3	Any	4	None	PORT_E	0
Any	NED_3	Any	3	None	PORT_E	0
Any	PORT_E	Any	4	4	NED_3	1
Any	PORT_E	Any	3	3	NED_3	1
Any	PORT_D	MAC_E	None	3	To table 1	0

(a) NED 4

Matching criteria				Actions		
Protocol	Input	Dst. MAC	Tunnel ID	Set Tunnel ID	Output	Table
Any	NED_4	Any	5	5	NED_1	0
					NED_2	
Any	NED_2 NED_1	Any	5	5	NED_4	0
Any	NED_2	Any	4	4	NED_4	0
Any	NED_4	Any	4	4	NED_2	0
Any	NED_1	Any	3	3	NED_4	0
Any	NED_4	Any	3	3	NED_1	0

(b) NED 3

Table 3: Rules for the red network in NEDs 3 and 4 after the Pods have started to communicate. As expected, NED 3 has no rule associated to a MAC address because it acts as an intermediate node in the red network. The ruleset in NED3 is the same as it was in Figure 1, The VNI 3 corresponds to the VNI 3 in Figure 6

Figure 5: The validation experiment scenario with the paths followed by the different data flows. The IDCO has been excluded from the figure for simplicity. The Pods A, B and C belong to the blue network, while D, E and F belong to the red network. The blue and red networks are completely isolated from each other. The data flows are multiplexed by tunnel id when traveling through the overlay network.

paths, which are the same as those that existed before the link went down. Following the computation, it installs the needed rules on the NEDs, going back to situation in Figure 5 (a).

A plot of the traffic separated by link and VXLAN VNI for the duration of this experiment is shown in Figure 6. When the link goes down, the network takes less than 5 seconds to recover, which means the packets start traveling through the new least-cost paths. During this recovery time, the packets are lost. When the network goes up again, the network takes around 8 seconds to use the new paths. During this time, no packets are lost because they keep traveling through the paths calculated for recovery. These times do not really depend on our solutions, but rather on the underlying network discovery and configuration technology, which could be changed. This is just an example to show how the data plane can be triggered to adapt to new paths. The trigger, in future implementations, could be a change in the desired paths to avoid congestion or as a result of an algorithm that computes the paths in a more intelligent way. The throughput in this graph is bigger than the goodput because of the overhead added by the headers in the packet.

Figure 6: The results of the experiment. The throughput (including the packet headers) is plotted for each VNI and link (only for the links between NEDs 1, 2 and 3). These flows can be visualized in Figure 5.

The network traffic in this validation has been generated with *iperf 2.0*⁴. The link blockage has been emulated by adding some rules to NED 1 and 3 firewalls to block the traffic between them. The broadcast traffic sent by B and C is formed by IP packets with a TTL field of 1, thus demonstrating the virtual networks provide link-layer rather than network-layer connectivity. To draw the graph with the results, we have captured all the packets in all the interfaces of the NEDs during the experiment and processed them using the *scapy* python library.

⁴Version 2.0 is the last version of iperf that supports changing the TTL

4.3. Performance considerations

It is possible to connect two pods running in a different clusters using Kubernetes services. However, the solution we propose has several already stated benefits: link-layer connectivity between Pods, the possibility to adapt the paths followed by the packets depending on the network status and the efficient distribution of multicast and broadcast traffic.

We would like to use this section to evaluate if our solution introduces any overhead that affects the available goodput with respect to using Kubernetes services, other than the impact that the extra packet headers for a VXLAN might have. To do so, we reuse the scenario in 3 deploying a NodePort service in the VM 2 to open a port from Pod A to the outside and execute an *iperf3.1* bandwidth test between Pod C and Pod A using both the flannel-provided interfaces and the interfaces used for our solution. The traffic through the flannel-provided interface using services will go through the L3 network for the control plane while the one that goes through our solution will use the L3 network for data plane (underlay). Both L3 networks have the same base bandwidth. Moreover, we add an unnecessary VXLAN between the VM 1 and the VM 2 in the L3 network the for control plane.

After repeating the execution of the tests 10 times, we get the results shown in Table 4. The performance is similar in both cases and we can, thus, demonstrate the proposed solution does not negatively affect the goodput. It is necessary to say the performance could change depending on the programmable switches in use (in this case OVS).

	Available goodput (Gbits/s)		
	Arithmetic mean	Maximum	Minimum
Kubernetes Services with VXLAN	1.79	1.83	1.75
Proposed solution	1.80	1.85	1.74

Table 4: The results of the obtained available goodput of the proposed solution when compared to using Kubernetes services with a VXLAN. The arithmetic mean, maximum and minimum values for the 10 executions are shown.

5. Conclusion

We have designed and implemented an SDN-based service that allows creating and deleting virtual link-layer networks between Pods deployed in different Kubernetes clusters. We have discussed and justified the benefits

and the gap this service fills. To functionally validate it, we have carried out an experiment that has been explained and illustrated.

The validation shows how the solution allows the management of the lifecycle of several virtual network between clusters, allowing Pods attached to them to communicate as if they were in the same local network. It also verifies how, given a programmable overlay network, it configures the least-cost paths for the packets in terms of hop count. Regarding this last fact, a future line of work is to add the option to choose the paths according to other metrics, like the congestion in each link, and adjust them dynamically.

Finally, there are other research lines to be explored. In the first place, the integration of the Overlay Manager entity that configures the NED overlay network. Secondly, the integration and validation of the solution with other new modern southbound protocols, like P4Runtime (The P4.org API Working Group (2020)) to connect the NEDs to the IDCO. Thirdly, a security analysis of the service and the introduction of new elements to support the secure management of the virtual networks and the establishment of trust relationships between the different actors, e.g., the cloud providers, the transport providers or the users of the service.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Raul Martin: Conceptualization, Software, Validation, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing- Review & Editing, Visualization. **Ivan Vidal:** Conceptualization, Validation, Resources, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Francisco Valera:** Conceptualization, Validation, Resources, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in this article.

Acknowledgment

This article has partially been supported by the NEMO European project, funded by the Horizon Europe programme with grant agreement 101070118, and by the 6G-INSPIRE project, funded by the Spanish State Research Agency with reference PID2022-137329OB-C42.

References

- Balalaie, A., Heydarnoori, A., Jamshidi, P., 2016. Microservices architecture enables devops: Migration to a cloud-native architecture. *IEEE Software* 33, 42–52. doi:10.1109/MS.2016.64.
- Clemm, A., Ciavaglia, L., Granville, L.Z., Tantsura, J., 2022. Intent-Based Networking - Concepts and Definitions. RFC 9315. doi:10.17487/RFC9315.
- Flannel Maintainer Community, 2023. flannel (version 0.22.0). <https://github.com/flannel-io/flannel>. Accessed: 17/12/2023.
- Garrison, J., Nova, K., 2017. Cloud native infrastructure: Patterns for scalable infrastructure and applications in a dynamic environment. "O'Reilly Media, Inc."
- Gonzalez, L.F., Vidal, I., Valera, F., Martin, R., Artalejo, D., 2023. A link-layer virtual networking solution for cloud-native network function virtualisation ecosystems: L2s-m. *Future Internet* 15. doi:10.3390/fi15080274.
- Gross, J., Ganga, I., Sridhar, T., 2020. Geneve: Generic Network Virtualization Encapsulation. RFC 8926. doi:10.17487/RFC8926.
- Han, B., Gopalakrishnan, V., Ji, L., Lee, S., 2015. Network function virtualization: Challenges and opportunities for innovations. *IEEE Communications Magazine* 53, 90–97. doi:10.1109/MCOM.2015.7045396.
- Joy, A.M., 2015. Performance comparison between linux containers and virtual machines, in: 2015 International Conference on Advances in Computer Engineering and Applications, pp. 342–346. doi:10.1109/ICACEA.2015.7164727.

- Kubernetes Network Plumbing Working Group, 2023. Multus CNI (version 4.0.2). <https://github.com/k8snetworkplumbingwg/multus-cni>. Accessed: 17/12/2023.
- Lasserre, M., Kompella, V., 2007. Virtual Private LAN Service (VPLS) Using Label Distribution Protocol (LDP) Signaling. RFC 4762. doi:10.17487/RFC4762.
- Li, T., Farinacci, D., Hanks, S.P., Meyer, D., Traina, P.S., 2000. Generic Routing Encapsulation (GRE). RFC 2784. doi:10.17487/RFC2784.
- Luksa, M., 2017. Kubernetes in action. Simon and Schuster.
- Mahalingam, M., Dutt, D., Duda, K., Agarwal, P., Kreeger, L., Sridhar, T., Bursell, M., Wright, C., 2014. Virtual eXtensible Local Area Network (VXLAN): A Framework for Overlaying Virtualized Layer 2 Networks over Layer 3 Networks. RFC 7348. doi:10.17487/RFC7348.
- Network Functions Virtualisation ETSI Industry Specification Group, 2019. Network Functions Virtualisation (NFV) Release 3; Management and Orchestration; Interface and Information Model Specification for Multi-Site Connectivity Services (GS NFV-IFA 032). Standard. ETSI.
- Open Networking Foundation, 2015. OpenFlow Switch Specification (version 1.5.1). Standard. Open Networking Foundation.
- Open Networking Foundation, 2021. Open Network Operating System (version 2.7.0). <https://opennetworking.org/onos/>. Accessed: 17/12/2023.
- OpenVPN Project, 2024. OpenVPN (version 2.6.10). <https://openvpn.net/>. Accessed: 17/12/2023.
- Potter, F., De Groot, A., 2019. The integration of ethernet virtual private network in kubernetes. <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:209382121>. Accessed: 17/12/2023.
- Rafiq, A., Mehmood, A., Song, W.C., 2020. Intent-based slicing between containers in sdn overlay network. J. Commun. 15, 237–244. doi:10.12720/jcm.15.3.237-244.

- Rekhter, Y., Kompella, K., 2007. Virtual Private LAN Service (VPLS) Using BGP for Auto-Discovery and Signaling. RFC 4761. doi:10.17487/RFC4761.
- Scazzariello, M., Ariemma, L., Battista, G.D., Patrignani, M., 2020. Megalos: A scalable architecture for the virtualization of network scenarios, in: NOMS 2020 - 2020 IEEE/IFIP Network Operations and Management Symposium, pp. 1–7. doi:10.1109/NOMS47738.2020.9110288.
- Stallings, W., 2015. Foundations of modern networking: SDN, NFV, QoE, IoT, and Cloud. Addison-Wesley Professional.
- Subratie, K., Aditya, S., Figueiredo, R.J., 2023. Edgevpn: Self-organizing layer-2 virtual edge networks. Future Generation Computer Systems 140, 104–116. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2022.10.007.
- Suo, K., Zhao, Y., Chen, W., Rao, J., 2018. An analysis and empirical study of container networks, in: IEEE INFOCOM 2018 - IEEE Conference on Computer Communications, pp. 189–197. doi:10.1109/INFOCOM.2018.8485865.
- The Antrea Contributors, 2024. Antrea (version 1.13.4). <https://antrea.io/>. Accessed: 17/12/2023.
- The Cilium Authors, Isovalent, 2024. Cilium (version 1.15.4). <https://cilium.io/>. Accessed: 17/12/2023.
- The Istio Authors, 2024. Istio (version 1.21.2). <https://istio.io/>. Accessed: 17/12/2023.
- The Linux Foundation, 2015. Open Container Initiative. <https://opencontainers.org/>. Accessed: 17/12/2023.
- The Open vSwitch Contributors, 2024. Open vSwitch (version 3.3.0). <https://www.openvswitch.org/>. Accessed: 17/12/2023.
- The OpenStack Community, 2024. OpenStack (version 2024.1 Caracal). <https://www.openstack.org/>. Accessed: 17/12/2023.
- The OVN contributors, 2024. Open Virtual Network (version 24.03.1). <https://www.ovn.org/en/>. Accessed: 17/12/2023.

- The P4.org API Working Group, 2020. P4Runtime Specification (version 1.3.0). Standard. ETSI. <https://p4.org/p4-spec/p4runtime/v1.3.0/P4Runtime-Spec.html>. Accessed: 17/12/2023.
- The Skupper Authors, 2024. Skupper (version 1.6.0). <https://skupper.io/>. Accessed: 17/12/2023.
- The Submariner Contributors, 2024. Submariner (version v0.17.1). <https://submariner.io/>. Accessed: 17/12/2023.
- Thönes, J., 2015. Microservices. IEEE Software 32, 116–116. doi:10.1109/MS.2015.11.
- Viswanathan, A., Rosen, E.C., Callon, R., 2001. Multiprotocol Label Switching Architecture. RFC 3031. URL: <https://www.rfc-editor.org/info/rfc3031>, doi:10.17487/RFC3031.
- Weaveworks, 2021. Weave Net (version 2.8.1). <https://www.weave.works/oss/net/>. Accessed: 17/12/2023.
- Yi, B., Wang, X., Li, K., k. Das, S., Huang, M., 2018. A comprehensive survey of network function virtualization. Computer Networks 133, 212–262. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comnet.2018.01.021>.